
I am Ben Bose, a Papalite, proud to be so. I was in Papal Seminary from 2007 to 2009 for Philosophy and from 2010 to 2013 for Theology. I was ordained priest on January 18, 2014. I rendered services as a priest in charge, prefect of studies in the minor seminary, assistant parish priest, assistant lecturer, and parish priest. At present, I am doing PhD in Canon Law at the Pontifical Gregorian University, Rome. Papal Seminary - the ‘Home of Love’- enabled me to love and respect human dignity and diversities. Well, in this write up, I would like to jot it down some of the reminiscences of my life in the Papal Seminary. As a Catholic priest, I always want to give priority to personal relationships with a human approach and I do believe that they are life-giving and life-promoting. Therefore, some of the personalities are mentioned here to add colours to my sharing and experience in the papal seminary.

Inspired Memories: The first and foremost, Fr Lionel Mascharhnes SJ, who was born in British India, (present Pakistan) and buried in the papal Seminary cemetery. All the Papalites would agree with me that he was a saintly priest, who had been the only rector of Papal Seminary, of Papal Atheneum (the present Jnana-Deepa), and of the De Nobili college. He was a synonym for punctuality. He used to be in the main Chapel vested with a stole before 6.45 am for the Mass. I still remember in 2008 his participation in the Community Day celebration wearing long a hat and directing the choir for the competition of the staff items. Once Cardinal Baselios Mar Clemees, a Papalite shared his experience of Fr Lionel as he was a seminarian in the Papal seminary. The story goes like this. It was a heavy rainy day, after supper as usual they were playing cards. Due to heavy downpours and wind, the windows were banking loudly but the thrill of the play does not make them notice of it. At that juncture, Fr Lionel enters and asked them an excuse, and latched the window. From this event, Cardinal Clemees pointed out the nobility and gentleness of the Fr Lionel. Such a living model influenced many of us.

Fr Francis Pereira SJ, was one of the leading Scripture scholars in India, who had taught St Paul (Gripped by God in Christ: The Mind and Heart of St. Paul) and the Gospel of Luke (Jesus, the human and humane face of God: A portrait of

Jesus in Luke's gospel). He was my spiritual father since philosophy days to my theology third year. Usually after the spiritual direction, he would hold on our both hands and make a short prayer which comprised in a nutshell all our sharing and concluded with asking for God's grace. It was always rejuvenating and his ever-smiling face in the corridors was mind-blowing. Though he had bypass heart surgery he had a very disciplined life, like everyday morning and evening walk through the corridors of Jnana Deepa and his daily celebration of the mass in his room etc. During his last days in Papal Seminary, he spent life in spiritual direction and committed to writing in Marathi for his people.

Community Day Celebrations: Another memorable moment in the Papal Seminary is obviously community day celebrations. It created lots of we-feeling and belongingness to the Home of Love, in which we had lots of fun, enjoyment, celebrations, discussions, boycotts, rehearsals even late nights. Joyfully I remember that when I was in the first-year philosophy for the competition of the extempore speech I won the prize, for which well in advance Bro Rojan Sebastian, then the captain of the team (now a priest of the diocese of Varanasi) conducted a trial session before the competition. *It also reminds me of Bro. Santan Dias (now the priest in the diocese of Jammu and Kashmir) who always came with his guitar to teach songs for the community. He used to learn songs from different languages including Tamil, Telugu, and Malayalam, and taught them to the entire community.* Though the whole community is divided into groups for the community day celebrations on 3rd of December morning we are ONE, celebrating the feast of our Patron, Saint Francis Xavier.

Common Programmes: We had wonderful living group floor gatherings, living group outings, overnight picnics, trekking, etc. filled with fun and joy. Another special characteristic of the students of the Papal Seminary is that just at least a week before the examinations the floors are silent, all are present in the rooms and lights are on even in the late nights which resulted in many of us being the top scorers in JD. In the community dialogues in the Papal Hall, we had a lot of discussions and heated arguments but always concluded with Papal anthem which united and gave us vigorous in life. The refrain is as follows

*Until our life is ended
Our prayer for thee shall be,
O Loving mother, Home of Love,
"God bless and prosper thee." (2)
Then the final chorus is:
Until our life is ended,
Thy charms may we recall,*

*God bless thee, dearest Home of Love
We'll love thee best of all (2).*

Philosophy Days: When I was doing my first-year philosophy, after Ajanta & Ellora study tour I got chicken pox and I was isolated in the infirmary. Since it is contagious, the rector Fr Pradeep Sequeira SJ, put up a notice stating not to visit me, but Fr Arockiadoss SJ, then the Dean of the Faculty of Theology visited me often and I realize the humane approach of the staff. Those days, my living group companion, Bro. Jacob Thundathil (now he is working in a parish in Italy) took care of me bringing me thrice a day with food and the needful things. Then by the grace of God, nobody else was affected in the community.

Fr Noel Sheth SJ was former rector of Papal Seminary, the renowned philosopher and Sanskrit scholar who taught Indian Philosophy and Buddhism. I was fascinated by his course on Buddhism, and as a result I had gone for 10 days of Vipassana Meditation. When I asked for permission though rector negated at first, then the intervention of Fr Noel Sheth made possible the Vipassana programme and met all the expenses by the Seminary. I realize from this small experience that how he was interested in the personal growth of the seminarians.

Theology Days: When I was doing my third-year of theology, I had to undergo surgery on the left ear, then Fr Noel contacted Dr. Durairaj, then his son Dr Manoj Durairaj whose friend is Dr Sandeep Karmarkar who is one of the best ENT specialists in Pune and gathered information for me. Thus, when I presented the matter to the minister Fr Jacob Kulangara SJ, and Fr Jose Thayil SJ, the Rector, they made it possible for me to have the best treatment for which in a special way I am grateful to them.

Another interesting personality is VM Jose sj, who is so silent and simple but he is powerful in action. I used to go to him for a friendly chat and personal sharing. He was regular for the game basketball and we used to play on the same team and his sure shots on the court made our game more interesting. Sometimes he challenged us with his simple actions like placing himself in the first row of the pews in the Chapel for the daily masses and for the rosary at the grotto in front of Papal Seminary. Then the gardening and beautification of the grotto had done by Bro. George Rhako (now priest in the diocese of Kohima). Many times I accompanied VM for visiting the poor families and supporting them financially in the neighborhoods. His simplicity and concern for the poor influenced me very much.

Fr Paul Parathazam, former student and professor in the Papal Seminary, and the present director of St John's National Academy of Health Sciences was our

teacher of Sociology of Religion, who challenged us with lots of criticism to reflect about ourselves and our identity. One of them is ‘be in the Church and not of the Church’ in order to be introspective. Another thought still I remember is that ‘the ruling ideas of the time is necessarily the ruling ideas of the ruling class’.

Fr Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ, is an amazing person with whom all the students feel at ease. His lectures on the human person and freedom are mind-blowing. His friendly nature and availability are very much appreciated. Still, I remember that when one of our companions’ father died, I went and knocked at his door around 2 am and presented the matter. Consequently, within no time he booked the flight ticket and made all the arrangements. Many of us had the freedom to get into his room and talk to him about anything at any time. He encouraged many of us to do masters in Philosophy and supported us very much in different aspects. He was the one who presented me to Fr Kurien Kunnumpuram SJ, to help out him in AUC during my Theology studies.

A Great Friendship: Fr Kurien became my mentor, spiritual father, and a good friend. The friendship began at the Papal Seminary and had strengthened and continued till his death. He still lives in me with his reflections and thoughts and memories we spent together. He was interested in my personal growth and influenced me very much especially when he returned to Christ Hall, Calicut, Kerala. I used to visit him at Christ Hall, we had taken me to his home and he visited me in my diocese and stayed with me in my home and parish as well. He guided me for the retreat before the priestly ordination and strengthened my theological understandings and convictions. As a young priest, when I had crises and challenges, he patiently listened to me and guided me. In a year, more or less five to six times I visited him in Calicut and stayed with him. In short, I was before him a naked baby with whom I enjoyed the freedom to share my life from alpha to omega. If I go on narrating the experiences and memories, I can go on and on with many pages and very many personal experiences and stories, which I do not want to write here now.

Well, as Fr Kurien was known for his three points, I wanted to share just three points: Firstly, he never spoke to me in our mother tongue when I was in Papal Seminary even when both of us were together. Once when I visited him in Calicut, I asked him about it and I noticed of you speaking in English always. The response was that I was in Papal Seminary for ALL students, I stood for the growth and freedom of the seminarians. He added where there is freedom, there is growth. It made me ponder over his vision and his sensitivity towards others. Secondly is his commitment. I had given my B.Th. thesis to him for the final correction, though he had a hectic schedule and few days left in the Papal Seminary in 2013, he

corrected and gave me in the early morning around 5 am before he left for the airport. It reminds me of how he was interested in my personal growth. Finally, it was my humble observation, though simple it has a value to be communicated to us that Fr Kurien even in his early 80s when he gets into our papal seminary chapel for the morning mass, used to kneel down before the Lord. It challenged me and made me think of his faith in God.

We are more or less 55 in number studying and working in Rome or in different parts of Italy. When we visit the Basilica St John Lateran, the Cathedral of diocese of Rome, we are reminded of Pope Leo XIII, whose corporal remaining preserved at the side of the altar as he was known for his social teaching, the encyclical '*Rerum Novarum*' for the whole world, but for a Papalite he is a great visionary and a missionary, who established the Papal Seminary with these words '*Filii tui India, administri tibi salutis*' (*Your own sons, O India, will be the heralds of your salvation*) in 1893. So visiting the basilica is a proud moment for each Papalite.

It is very challenging to 'Live authentically and Die cheerfully.' It is one of the quotes that I read in one of the documents on the history of Papal Seminary during the orientation programme in 2007. But there is another caption, 'Peace begins with a smile' which is found on the photo of Mother Teresa at the corridor of the Papal Seminary refectory which is still in mind to inspire us.

Ben Bose C.C., a Catholic Priest belongs to the diocese of Neyyattinkara, Kerala, India. His major seminary formation was at Papal Seminary and obtained BPh. in 2009 and BTh. in 2013 from Jnana-Deepa, Pune. He holds BA in Sociology from the University of Kerala, MA in Philosophy from IGNOU and MA in English Language and Literature from the University of Kerala. He was ordained on 18th January 2014. He was a priest in charge, the prefect of studies in the minor seminary, vocation promoter, assistant parish priest, parish priest and associate professor in English Language and Literature. He secured a licentiate in Canon Law from the Pontifical University of Holy Cross, Rome in 2022 and is currently pursuing Ph.D in Canon Law at the Pontifical Gregorian University, Rome.